

THE ROLE AND IMPORTANCE OF MODERN METHODS IN LANGUAGE TEACHING

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Annotation: This article discusses the role and importance of modern methods in language teaching. Based on linguistic data, the author analyzes the problem on the basis of existing scientific literature and explores the specifics of the role and importance of modern methods in language teaching.

Keywords: Linguistics, countries, education, methods, development, innovation, methodology.

Introduction:

Today, foreign language skills are becoming an integral part of vocational education. Due to the high level of cooperation with foreign partners in various fields, the demand for language learning is high.

The ability to use information technology and modern teaching methods helps to quickly understand new materials. By combining different methods, the teacher will be able to solve specific educational programs. In this regard, teachers and students need to become familiar with modern methods of language teaching. As a result, they develop the skills to choose the most effective ways to achieve their goals. Using a variety of teaching and learning methods can be effective. Teaching takes place in small steps and is based on the student's existing knowledge system. As time goes on, there is more and more innovation in every field.

Main part:

Language learning is one of the most important areas of human society. Language, which is a means of communication, can be practiced in a natural environment, whether in the family, in the community, or in an organized manner. Knowledge of linguistic

phenomena is taught theoretically. Knowledge of languages, especially multilingualism, is especially important in today's world of international relations. Pupils and students studying in our country usually learn three languages. These languages are referred to by special names. These are: native language, second language, and foreign language. Mother tongue is the first language that plays a special role in the formation of thinking. When it comes to the second language, it is considered the language of the brothers and sisters of other nationalities.

Language teaching methods have a history of more than 200 years as a science. During this period, different approaches to language teaching methods have been observed. One such view belongs to academician L.V. Shcherba. According to him, any methodology of teaching science, although it is a science, is not a theoretical science. He solves practical problems. In particular, the methodology of language teaching is based not only on the evidence of psychology, but also on the research of general and specific linguistics. If linguistics deals with the laws of origin and movement of linguistic phenomena, the methodology answers the question of what must be done to put into practice the necessary linguistic phenomenon based on these laws. The most valuable books on methodology have also been written by linguists.

These include G. Suite, one of the great phonetists of the nineteenth century and the great English linguist; Bruns and Brealya, prominent Englishman and well-known phoneticist V.Fiyotor and others. Academician L.V. Shcherba and his teacher, the great linguist I.A. Baudouin-de-Courtoine, and their students studied the methodology of language teaching in Russia. Psychologists have a different approach to foreign language teaching methods. Professor V.A. Artemov gave a valuable opinion on the relationship between methodology and psychology. In his view, psychology provides material for methodology. Methodology is the study of how a teacher teaches. Psychology, on the other hand, deals with how students master a subject. But I can't completely agree with that. Because the teacher is in the process of teaching, and the student is experiencing certain mental processes and situations during the mastery

process, they are exposed to and influenced by the laws of psychology, whether they want to or not.

We now understand that improving the quality and effectiveness of education is the foundation of our future development. The teacher should be creative in his / her subject during the lesson. The teacher should organize the lesson using modern pedagogical technologies and methods.

There is a growing interest in the use of pedagogical and information technologies in the educational process.

Results and Discussions:

There are several types of interactive methods available today, and the educational process is based on these methods. Pedagogical technology is a system of orderly actions that leads to pre-planned results.

There are many types of teaching methods. Students need to master the learning information, understand the topic, reinforce their knowledge through lectures, stories, explanations, and video tutorials.

Boomerang technology can be used for new topics. This technology allows students to work with texts in the classroom, to memorize the material studied, to narrate, to express ideas freely, to gain a lot of information in a short time, and to learn during the lesson. aimed at assessing all students by the anteat. Objective: How to answer the text and questions in the materials distributed through discussion and various questions, monitoring and evaluation of mastery. Give students a chance to get their grades.

Application of technology. Practical lessons and conversational discussions can be used individually in small groups and in groups. Materials used in the lesson: handouts for students (ie short texts, pictures, information on the topic).

The teacher asks students questions and conducts an oral survey. Based on the answers to the questions, the total scores of the groups will be determined. The total points earned by the groups will be determined. The total points earned by the groups are divided equally among the group members.

Interactive ("inter" - to interact with "ast" - to move) - to interact, to start a conversation with someone.

Interactive teaching methods

- is a special form of organization of cognitive and communicative activities in which learners are involved in the process of learning, they have the opportunity to understand and think about what they know and think.

We know that in the current educational process, the student must be a subject. Focusing on more interactive methods will increase the effectiveness of education. One of the most important requirements for language classes is to teach students to think independently. Today, English language teachers use the following innovative methods, drawing on the experience of educators in the United States and the United Kingdom:

- "Creative Problem"

Solving) to use this method, the beginning of the story is read and the end is referred to the judgment of the students;

- Merry Riddles is an important part of teaching English to students, where they learn words they are unfamiliar with and find the answer to a riddle;

- Quick answers help to increase the effectiveness of the lesson;

- "Warm-up exercises" - the use of various games in the classroom to engage students in the lesson;

- Pantomime can be used in a class where very difficult topics need to be explained, or when students are tired of writing exercises;

- A chain story method helps to develop students' oral skills;

- Acting characters This method can be used in all types of lessons. Professionals such as Interpreter, Translator, Writer, and Poet can participate in the class and talk to students;

- "Thinkers meeting" of poets and writers such as U. Shakespeare, A. Navoi, R. Burns

Can "offer". At the same time, using the words of wisdom they say in class will help young people grow up to be perfect people; Literature:

- The method of "When pictures speak" is more convenient and helps to teach English, to develop students' oral speech, it is necessary to use thematic pictures;
- Quiz cards are distributed according to the number of students and allow all students to attend classes at the same time, which saves time.

As we have seen, each innovative technology has its own set of advantages. All of these methods involve collaboration between teacher and student, active participation of the student in the educational process.

Conclusion:

In conclusion, modern language teaching is aimed at forming a more cultured individual who has the skills to self-analyze and systematize new knowledge. Innovative methods are an integral part of modernizing the entire system. With this in mind, teachers can become acquainted with the most advanced approaches and then combine them and use them in their work to achieve significant growth in the education system.

The study of languages is a multifaceted doctrine, in the process of which a person undergoes complex psychological changes. In particular, there is a process of comparing the mother tongue with another language. Different teaching methods and technologies are used in this process. With the help of modern pedagogical technologies, comparative teaching of a foreign language with the native language gives effective results. Language teaching requires knowledge of its methods.

Methodology and technology play an important role in language learning. There are different methods of methodical science in the organization of the lesson. The most widely used methods of language teaching are: the method of communicative didactics, the method of organizing intercultural communication and the method of organizing exercises. The three methods are closely related and complementary. Because the science of methodology is related to the science of didactics, the study of languages is based on communicativeness, and the method of communicative didactics emerges.

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